

FAMILY COHESION AND BULLY VICTIMIZATION AS PREDICTORS OF INTERPERSONAL AND INTRAPERSONAL FACTORS OF SCHOOL CHILDREN

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ABSTRACT

The present study is an attempt to explore the relationship between family cohesion, bullying victimization and emotional behavioral problems in school children. It was hypothesized that high family cohesion resulted in bullying victimization and emotional behavioral problems. The data was collected through purposive sampling of non-probability sampling. The sample of 225 children (53.8 % boys, 46.2% girls) with the age range of 9-17 (M= 14.78, SD=2.49) were from schools of Lahore. The measures of current study were comprised of Family Cohesion (Zahra & Saleem, 2021), Bullying Victimization Scale (Amjad, 2014), Emotional Behavioral Problem Scale (Saleem & Mahmood, 2011) and demographic Performa. The result showed that family cohesion has low but positive and significant relationship with bullying victimization. Emotional behavioral problems have significant, positive but low relationship with family cohesion. There is significant and moderately positive relationship between emotional behavioral problems and bullying victimization. It was also found from t-test that girls have more emotional behavioral problems than boys. To conclude, family and school both have significant role to play in children's life as minor inconvenience in any of them leads to mental health issues.

INTRODUCTION

Childhood and adolescence is a crucial stage in a person's life, events happening in this phase keeps promoting, enhancing and maintaining mental health. During these years of life individual went through various challenges that has great impact on growth and overall wellbeing. Children face academic pressure, social struggles, peer pressure, identity formation, physical changes, self-esteem and bullying during these years of life (Beckman & Hellstrom, 2021). A child can be prone to different mental health issues at this stage of life and in a lot of cases these issues continue through adult life (Orben et al., 2022), The everyday life of adolescents and children is affected by personal characteristics and social setting in which they grow up

including their families and schools, schools play a vital role in development of child (Tucker et al., 2015). As the matter of fact, mostly mental health issues are developed by the age to 14 years which is a school going age for children (Gore et al., 2011). Nevertheless, of a student's gender, background and ethnicity school life is demanding; burdensome and challenging for all students in different manners for the reason that students encounter with different issues in school as by starting school children are moving from the protected, familiar environment of family into a new, difficult, and unpredictable environment of school (Gobena, 2020). Some of the problems are mild and moderate while other are very serious that they cause stress,

disorientation, absence of control and these problems become unmanageable. Difficulties in school can lead to psychological problems and common issues faced by the students during school age are emotional behavioral problems. (Schulte-Körne, 2016).

Emotional and behavioral problems enclose a large amount of deviant, disturbing and maladaptive emotions, thoughts and actions (Magai et al., 2018). Emotional behavioral problems are divided into externalizing and internalizing problems. In internalized problems, child show the symptoms of depression, anxiety, social withdrawal and somatic issues. While, in externalizing problems child shows disturbing, disruptive and deviant behaviors (Saleem et al., 2021). There are certain characteristics held by the child who is suffering from emotional behavioral problems which include impulsiveness, short attention period, aggression, refuse to follow advises and rules, disrespectful behavior, arguments, being frustrated, not ready to take responsibility, withdrawal, immaturity, difficulty in forming relations, angry mood, age-inappropriate behaviors and learning issues in schools. There is no single reason behind the emotional behavior problems, biological, developmental, cognitive, behavioral and cultural factors contribute to the disturbing emotions and behaviors of children (Ogundele, 2018). Problem Suppression-Facilitation model of cultural influence (Weisz et al., 1987) shows that children who are from collectivist and traditional culture have more emotional problems than behavioral problems and children who are from individualistic culture shows more externalizing problems then internalizing problems. As Pakistani culture is collectivist so by Problem Suppression-Facilitation model children are supposed to show more internalized problems (Malik, et al. 2010). Social environmental factors have major influence on the emotional and behavioral development of children. As authoritative parenting has significant negative association with problem causing behaviors. And on the other side children whose parents were authoritarian and permissive, either parents or maybe either father only or mother only have positive relationship with problem causing behaviors. Children learn to get through in society with the aid of family cohesion (Cobham et al., 2016).

Family cohesion contains the emotional connection within the family members and the independence experienced by individuals within the family system (Olson DH et al., 2011). Family cohesion has a profound impact on school students and on their academic performance. Child's relationship with parents is the most essential factor that shapes a child's behavior and his personality (Valić & Brajša, 2018) Students who go through the academic problems due to an unsupportive family, have more risk to develop feelings of inferiority and failure while staying at home (Yunus et al., 2014). Characteristics of family cohesion include attachment, honesty togetherness and a demonstrative connection of family towards each other. Many researches have examined that if the family is supportive and focuses on their child as a responsibility, the child will be connected with school and will not be a part of bullying victimization (Hawkins et al., 2021).

Bullying is basically a serious general health issue in the world among children. Bullying victimization is normally expressed as revelation to deeds which have frequent adverse effect from more than one different individual. The large number of bullying victims is submissive. When we differentiate the victims of bully and bullies, victims are more likely to lead the extent of isolation and worry, while bullies are the least. Social rank of bullies is high, and victims are low. Nevertheless, class fellows keep away from bully-victims the most (Shetgiri, 2013). Eastern culture comprises numerous social cultures, countries, and states. In eastern cultures like Turkey, Pakistan, India, China, Russia etc, children are bullied on the basis of cast, color, height and weight etc. bullying on appearance is very common in eastern cultures due to which children are influenced physically and also mentally. Most of the children have low self-esteem and poor confidence if they are a victim of bullying. Characteristic of bullying victimization includes self-doubting personality and peer rejection. Those children who are quiet, unresponsive, and nervous have higher rates of becoming a victim of bullying-And children who are bullied once, they become insecure and cry more frequently even if bullying does not occur. Bullied children hardly have friends. A child who is bullied is less likely to develop a group of friends if we compare to those peers that are not

a part of bullying victimization (Thill, 2020). Bullying can be minimized through family support. If the family is supportive and be responsible for giving right advice and motivation to their children can help them to recover from bullying victimization or they will never become a part of bullying. Having a better relationship with family heads to have a better connection at school instead of becoming a victim of bullying. School age is a span of expeditious cognitive, biological and neurological conversion subsequently leave a silent impression on psychological functioning and relationships of child. During this stage, relationship shared by parents and peers of child are most dominant among all relationships. People deduce that bullying is a complication for schools alone, it is not right because parents also have a very significant character to play. The effects of victimization are devastating for student's mental health. Being the victim of bullying, will lead to many mental health issues out of which

emotional and behavioral problems are common in school children (Metzler et al., 2017). In essence, the early school and family experiences results in influencing children life on the whole. Child face bullying or other issues in school therefore its responsibility of parents to provide the supportive environment to their children especially during early years of their life.

Method

Correlational research design was used to examine the association amidst variables,

Participants

A sample of 225 participants, both boys and girls from different schools were taken for data collection. Data was collected form school going students of Lahore through questionnaires. In present study purposive sampling technique of non-probability sampling was used to collect data from participants. 121 boys and 104 girls were selected from schools of Lahore.

Table No. 2

Frequencies and Percentage of Demographic Variables of Participants (N=225)

Sr.no	Variables	f	%
1	Age	9-12	44.40
		13-17	55.60
2	Gender	Boy	53.80
		Girl	46.20
3	Family System	Nuclear	66.20
		Joint	33.80
4	No. of Siblings	3 or less than 3	62.20
		More than 3	37.80
5	Father Qualification	Matric or less than matric	57.30
		Intermediate	11.60
		Graduate	16.90
		Masters	10.20
		PHD	4.00
6	Mother Qualification	Matric or less than matric	64.90
		Intermediate	9.30
		Graduate	12.90
		Masters	10.20
		PHD	2.70

Note: f=Frequencies and %=Percentages

The above table shows the frequencies and percentages of the demographic variables of the study. There were 6 demographic variables in the study. The age range of the participants was categorized into two groups. It was found that there were more participants in 13-17 (55.6%) group than 9-12 (44.4%) group. It is clear from above table that slightly more boys (53.8%) than girls (44.2%) participated in this study. Greater portion of participants were living in nuclear family (66.2%) than joint family system (33.8%) To some extent, more participants were found with more than three numbers of siblings (37.8%). Likewise, some more children were found whose father's qualification was matric or primary (57.3%). Some more children were found whose mother's qualification was matric or primary (64.9%).

Inclusion and Exclusion Criteria

Inclusion criteria of research was

- Both girls and boys were participated.
- Participants who have age range between 9 to 17 years were recruited for the study.

Exclusion criteria of research was

- Children who have any acute or chronic condition that would limit the ability of child to participate in the study will be excluded.
- Children who have single or divorced parents.

Measures

Demographic form

A self-report demographic form was used to collect demographic information which includes informed consent, age, gender, family system, qualification of parents and number of siblings.

Family Cohesion Scale (Zahra & Saleem, 2021)

The indigenously scale of family cohesion was used to assess the family cohesion. It consists of 51 items. Items are measured on 4-point rating in which 1 means 'never and 5 means 'very much'. There are 4 factors of family cohesion from which we have used 3 factors out of 4 that are, mutual support, sharing and parental involvement. Internal consistency of scale is 0.90.

Bullying Victimization Scale (Amjad, 2014)

The indigenously developed scale of bullying victimization was used to assess the children who have been the target of bullying. It consists of 32

items including 3 factors as emotional, physical and verbal bullying. It uses Likert scale ranging from 1 to 4 where 1 stands for "never" and 4 stands for "very much". Reliability of scale is 0.91.

School Children Problem Scale (Saleem & Mahmood, 2011)

This indigenously developed scale of emotional behavioral problem measures the emotional behavioral problems of children. It consists of 44 items. This scale measures 6 different dimensions of emotional, behavioral problems included "anxious, academic problems, aggression, social withdrawal, feeling of rejection and psychosomatic complains. Test re-test reliability of this scale was 0.79. It is a four-point rating scale from 0-4 including never, rarely, sometimes and often respectively.

Procedure

Permission was taken from the departmental committee for research approval. Permission was also taken from authors of scales, which was used for this research purpose for data collection. After getting permission respective schools will be contacted to receive permission to collect data. Data was collected from some private schools of Lahore. When data collection was started, consent from participants was taken either they want to give data or not. They were asked for any query while responding to the items. The main purpose of the study was explained through informed consent and assures their approval. Data was collected through questionnaires of each variable and demographic sheet will attach with them. The complete instruction regarding scale was mentioned in questionnaires. All ethics were followed during the process of research. Data was added in SPSS and statistical analysis was run. All findings were then being reported in tables and figures.

Results

Correlation Study

- It is hypothesized that there will likely to be a negative relationship between family cohesion and bullying victimization and emotional behavior problems in school children.
- It is hypothesized that there will likely to be a positive relationship between bullying victimization and emotional behavior problems in school children.

The above table shows the Mean, standard deviation and Correlation values of the factors and total of scales used in the research. The table shows that emotional behavioral problem scale has significant, positive but very low relationship with family cohesion scale ($r=2.74$, $p< 0.001$). There is significant and moderately positive relationship between emotional behavioral problems scale and bullying victimization scale ($r= 0.676$, $p< 0.001$). The family cohesion scale has very low but positive and significant relationship with bullying victimization ($r= 0.262$, $p< 0.001$). All factors of emotional behavioral problems scale have significant correlation with family cohesion, bullying victimization scales and their factors. Correlation

between bullying victimization factors and emotional behavioral problems, family cohesion scales and their factors is also significant. Mutual support and family cohesion has significant and high positive correlation ($r= .727$, $p<0.001$). There is significant and very low negative correlation between mutual support and feelings of rejection ($r= -.151$, $p<0.001$). There is significant and very low positive correlation between sharing and emotional behavioral, family cohesion, bullying victimization scales and their factors. Parental involvement has significant correlation with emotional behavioral problems, family cohesion, bullying victimization scales and their factors except mutual support.

Variables	N	M	SD	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	13	14	15
EBPtotal	225	89.24	24.55	1														
FCStotal	225	85.82	15.64	.274**	1													
BVStotal	225	52.02	17.27	.676**	.262**	1												
F1EBPtotal	225	24.36	7.366	.880**	.241**	.565**	1											
F2EBPtotal	225	15.84	5.556	.852**	.190**	.599**	.654**	1										
F3EBPtotal	225	18.97	6.443	.804**	.224**	.591**	.561**	.678**	1									
F4EBPtotal	225	12.74	3.915	.804**	.266**	.527**	.595**	.610**	.528**	1								
F5EBPtotal	225	8.924	3.694	.771**	.245**	.588**	.657**	.607**	.477**	.628**	1							
F6EBPtotal	225	8.395	2.978	.724**	.170**	.357**	.618**	.519**	.530**	.536**	.502**	1						
F1BVS	225	21.80	7.755	.642**	.237**	.945**	.546**	.550**	.564**	.486**	.561**	.360**	1					
F2BVS	225	17.81	6.603	.615**	.189**	.924*	.507**	.577**	.535**	.498**	.497**	.309**	.798**	1				
F3BVS	225	12.40	4.458	.593**	.322**	.862**	.488**	.511**	.518**	.460**	.566**	.298**	.740**	.712**	1			
F1FCS	225	42.43	8.972	.058**	.727**	.020	-.056	-.077	.039**	-.039*	-.151*	-.045	.018	-.019	.075	1		
F2FCS	225	19.33	5.803	.244**	.801**	.195**	.230**	.176**	.147*	.240**	.266**	.149*	.172**	.152*	.233**	.413**	1	
F3FCS	225	24.05	7.243	.469**	.618**	.383**	.407**	.365**	.317**	.430**	.503**	.305**	.351**	.310**	.416**	.001	.417**	1

Table: 3

Mean, Standard Deviation and Correlation between scales of Family Cohesion, Bullying Victimization, and Emotional Behavioral Problems.

Note: * $p< .05$, ** $p< .01$, *** $p<0.01$, M= Mean, SD= Standard Deviation, *EBPF1*= anxiousness, *EBPF2*= academic problems, *EBPF3*= aggression, *EBPF4*= withdrawal, *EBPF5*= feelings of rejection, *EBPF6*= somatic problems, *BVSF1*=

emotional bullying, *BVSF2*= verbal bullying, *BVSF3*= physical bullying, *FCSF1*= mutual support, *FCSF2*= sharing, *FCSF3*= parental involvement.

Regression Analysis

- It is hypothesized that bullying victimization and family cohesion will likely to be the predictors of emotional behavioral problems in school children.

Table No. 3

Hierarchical Regression Analysis of Demographics, Family Cohesion, Bullying Victimization and Emotional Behavioral Problems

Models	B	95% CI for B		SEB	β	R ²	ΔR^2
		LL	UL				
Step 1						.04	.04
Age	.73	-1.05	2.52	.91	.05**		
Gender	9.34	2.92	15.75	3.25	.19		
Family system	1.74	-5.00	8.49	3.42	.03		
Step 2						.26	.22
Mutual Support	-.34	-.71	.02	.18	-.12		
Sharing	.49	-.11	1.09	.31	.11		
Parental Involvement	1.36	.92	1.81	.22	.41***		
Step 3						.54	.29
Emotional Bullying	.97	.45	1.51	.26	.31***		
Verbal Bullying	.79	.19	1.38	.31	.21		
Physical Bullying	.61	-.21	1.41	.41	.11`		

Note: B= Unstandardized Coefficient Beta, LL= Lower Limit, UL= Upper Limit, SEB= Standardized Error Beta, β = Beta, R²= R Square, ΔR^2 = Adjusted R Square *p<.05, **p<.01, ***p<.001

The above table shows that girl's gender, family cohesion and bullying victimization are predictors of emotional behavioral problems. They just predict school population (N=225). While doing regression, family cohesion and bullying victimization were kept as independent variables whereas emotional behavioral problems were kept as dependent variable. In first model, the demographics were added to identify their role in emotional behavioral problems. Only gender was found as the predictor of EBP. In the second model family cohesion was tested as the

predictor of EBP along with its subscales. Parental involvement was emerged as the predictor of EBP whereas, third model bullying victimization along with its subscales were added to test them as predictors of EBP. Emotional bullying was found out as a predictor of EBP.

Therefore, girls who have more parental involvement and experiences more emotional bullying will be more tend towards having emotional behavioral problems. Results of regression analysis are consistent with hypotheses.

Gender Differences

- It is hypothesized that there will be more emotional behavioral problems in girls than boys.

Table No. 4

Mean, Standard Deviation, t value, significance, Lower Limit and Upper Limit of Confidence Interval and Cohen's d of Family Cohesion, Bullying Victimization and Emotional Behavioral Problems (N=225)

No.	Boys			Girls			T	P	95% CI		Cohen's d
	N	M	SD	N	M	SD			LL	UL	
FCSF1	121	41.81	9.08	104	43.15	8.83	.27	.760	-3.69	1.03	-1.34
FCSF2	121	19.03	5.39	104	19.68	6.26	.41	.228	-2.18	0.88	-0.65
FCSF3	121	23.21	5.92	104	25.04	8.44	.05	.000***	-3.72	0.07	-1.83
FCS	121	84.06	14.71	104	87.87	16.51	.07	.739	-7.91	0.28	-3.82
BVSF1	121	21.82	7.36	104	21.78	8.23	.99	.595	-2.02	2.08	0.03
BVSF2	121	17.69	6.63	104	17.96	6.59	.76	.870	-2.01	1.48	-0.27
BVSF3	121	12.14	4.15	104	12.70	4.79	.35	.434	-1.73	0.61	-0.56
BVS	121	51.65	16.38	104	52.45	18.34	.73	.664	-5.36	3.76	-0.79

EBPF1	121	22.97	6.86	104	25.99	7.63	.01	.127	-4.93	-1.12	-3.02
EBPF2	121	15.41	5.33	104	16.34	5.79	.21	.206	-2.40	0.52	-0.94
EBPF3	121	18.11	5.83	104	19.98	6.98	.03	.083	-3.56	-0.18	-1.87
EBPF4	121	12.19	3.45	104	13.39	4.33	.02	.001***	-2.23	-0.18	-1.20
EBPF5	121	8.28	3.11	104	9.66	4.17	.01	.000***	-2.33	-0.14	-1.37
EBPF6	121	8.09	2.80	104	8.74	3.15	.11	.181	-1.42	0.14	-0.64
EBP	121	85.06	21.06	104	94.11	27.38	.01	.003**	-15.43	-2.68	-9.06

Note: * $p < .05$, ** $p < .01$, *** $p < .001$, $n = \text{no.}$ of participants, $M = \text{mean}$. $SD = \text{standard deviation}$, $LL = \text{lower limit}$ and $UL = \text{upper limit}$, $EBPF1 = \text{anxiousness}$, $EBPF2 = \text{academic problems}$, $EBPF3 = \text{aggression}$, $EBPF4 = \text{withdrawal}$, $EBPF5 = \text{feelings of rejection}$, $EBPF6 = \text{somatic problems}$, $BVSF1 = \text{emotional bullying}$, $BVSF2 = \text{verbal bullying}$, $BVSF3 = \text{physical bullying}$, $FCSF1 = \text{mutual support}$, $FCSF2 = \text{sharing}$, $FCSF3 = \text{parental involvement}$.

T-test was conducted to compare the significant difference in emotional behavioral problems, bullying victimization and family cohesion of boys and girls. Significant difference of emotional behavioral problems was found in boys and girls ($t(223) = -2.80$, $p = .003$) in the scores with mean score for boys ($M = 85.06$, $SD = 21.06$) was low than girls ($M = 94.11$, $SD = 27.38$). Parental involvement which is factor of family cohesion, there was significant difference found in boys and girls ($t(223) = -1.90$, $p = .000$) in the scores with score for boys ($M = 84.06$, $SD = 14.71$) was low than girls ($M = 87.87$, $SD = 16.51$). No significant difference was found in boys and girls bullying victimization ($t(223) = -3.45$, $p = .730$) in the scores with score for boys ($M = 51.65$, $SD = 16.38$) was low than scores for girls ($M = 52.45$, $SD = 18.34$). In Withdrawal, there was significant difference found in boys and girls. ($t(223) = -2.322$, $p = .021$) in the scores with score for boys ($M = 12.19$, $SD = 3.45$) was less than girls ($M = 13.39$, $SD = 4.33$). In Feelings of rejection, there was significant difference found in boys and girls ($t(223) = -2.825$, $p = .005$) in the scores with mean score for boys ($M = 8.28$, $SD = 3.11$) was less than girls ($M = 9.66$, $SD = 4.17$). No significant relation was shown between other variables.

- bullying victimization and emotional behavioral problems in school children.

Discussion

School life is a phase of biological, psychological and social growth which demands adaptations in

ever-changing expectations and failing in adjustment increase the chances of a school child to be at the risk of emotional behavioral problems (Ma et al., 2018; Saleem & Mahmood, 2011). During school life, living in social pressure leads to different kind of issues that may take child to emotional behavioral problems (Saleem et al., 2019). Along with other health issues, bullying victimization also has great effect on emotional well-being of children (Naveed et al., 2020). Therefore, the current study aimed to explore the relationship between Family Cohesion, Bullying Victimization and Emotional Behavioral Problems in School Children. Objective of this study was to find out gender differences associated with Emotional Behavioral Problems in School Children. Mean age of the study was 14 years and standard deviation is 2.49, which show that most of the participants are in their early adolescence.

In present study, correlation analysis shows that the family cohesion has low but positive and significant relationship with bullying victimization. Emotional behavioral problems have significant, positive but low relationship with family cohesion. There is significant and moderately positive relationship between emotional behavioral problems and bullying victimization. Results are not consistent with hypotheses. As sometimes increased family cohesion leads to bullying victimization because mothers become overprotective for their children this inhibits their development independence and skills to go through social environment and in this way child become easy prey for bullies (Berdondini & Smith, 2005). Most of the researchers only discuss that low family cohesion leads to bullying victimization because those children who have harsh, pessimistic, uncooperative and neglecting parents are doubtlessly become prey to bullies. Present research fills the gap as it shows high family cohesion leads to bullying victimization because if parents are overprotective, they also increase

the chance of their child to become the victim of bullying. In our culture children who arrive from very defensive and shielding families lean to get victimized at schools, for the reason that, parents always solve the problem that arrives in their child life child will not up to establish skills to cope and may become effortless prey for bullies. A large number of studies reported the association between bullying victimization and health problems in school children. Being bullied has a big mental and emotional impression, child feel disliked, avoided, and lonely. Poor mental health leads to emotional behavioral problems. Bullying victimization leads to physical and psychological health issues (Mohseny et al., 2019). One research reported that children who experience bullying had more distress and more emotional behavioral problems (Gustafsson et al., 2017). In this way, researches prove those overprotective families' leads to bullying and experiencing bullying further leads to emotional behavioral problems.

It seems that results of regression analysis show that girls have more emotional behavioral problems than boys due to higher extent of family cohesion. Girls living in high level of family connectedness may lead them to be less responsible in their lives. Results are consistent with hypothesis. More often, several researches have proven that over controlling and over possessive families' give rise to bullying and facing bullying promotes emotional behavioral problems. Families become very controlling when it comes to the female gender. Emotional bullying and parental involvement lead to emotional behavioral problems. Most of girls take emotional bullying extremely serious and start developing negative emotions that leads to emotional behavioral problems. Emotional bullying can cause long term scars on girls. Girls who are emotionally bullied frequently can also go in isolation or can even try to attempt suicide. On the other side, if the parenting style is not good enough to reach the criteria of fulfilling the basic concentration towards the child will also give rise to emotional behavioral problems. As girls are born with a sensitive nature, such parenting styles can be even painful for them. In collectivist cultures, girls are taught that they should compromise the overprotective behaviors and actions of their family members, but boys are not brought up in the same way. If girls are

controlled by their families or if their families are being overprotective, they consider it as societal learning or believe that it is for their better wellbeing (Meyer, 2022).

Independent sample t-test results suggest that girls have more emotional behavioral problems than boys. These results are agreeing with the hypothesis (Angold et al., 2002; Emami et al., 2007; Rescorla et al., 2007). Although in many societies, girls are getting their rights. But in a traditional collectivistic society, like Pakistan, where society plays a very important role in developing the ways of living, it is expected only from the girls to fulfill the societal and religious norms. Society expects only from girls to obey their parents and take care of families' honor. That is the reason society put a lot of restrictions on them. All of these families' and societal demands put girls at the greater likelihood of developing emotional and behavioral problems (Saleem & Mehmood, 2013). Results also show that there is more withdrawal and feelings of rejection in girls than boys. All of these are internalized problems and there are researches which support this notion that females are more vulnerable of developing internalized problems than men (Hoftmann et al., 2004). Another study also finds out that rate of internalized problems in female is high than men. There are some social mechanisms that help to explain the differences between gender regarding emotional and behavioral problems. These mechanisms include differences in the rearing and lifestyles of girls and boys. Difference between boys and girls regarding emotional behavioral problems has been shown in epidemiological and clinical studies (Bartels et al., 2011).

Conclusion

School life is a crucial stage in which different psychological, social, emotional and biological changes occur. School children face many difficulties and there are many risk factors for them. The unhealthy relationship with family, unhealthy environment in school is also a risk factor that leads to inability to interact within their society and family, it also leads them to emotional behavioral problems. Family and school both have significant role to play in children's life as minor inconvenience in any of them leads to mental health issues. But if

children cope with these issues they can deal with their problems.

Limitations and Recommendations

Research findings have low generalizability because only schools of Lahore were observed.

Children from private schools of Lahore were only approached. Because some government schools were closed at the time of our data collection and some government schools did not allow us to collect data.

As our scales were in Urdu language it became difficult for some children to understand, so assistance was provided to them in reading items of scales.

Some psychological strategies can be highlighted in order to make the children understand to cope with their transitional age.

The perspective of parents and teachers could be taken.

Awareness can develop about the problems of children in school.

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